

Supplementary material for
*Fault detection in a swarm of physical robots
based on behavioural outlier detection*

Danesh Tarapore¹, Jon Timmis², Anders Lyhne Christensen³

¹ School of Electronics and Computer Science, University of Southampton, Southampton, U.K.

² York Robotics Laboratory and the Department of Electronics, University of York, York, U.K.;
and Faculty of Technology, University of Sunderland, Sunderland, U.K.

³Embodied Systems for Robotics and Learning at the Maersk Mc-Kinney Moller Institute, University of Southern Denmark (SDU), Odense, Denmark; and Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (ISCTE-IUL), Lisbon, Portugal

S1 Experiment data

Performance logs of all fault-detection experiment data is available at <https://goo.gl/EjiW9c>. Video recordings of all the experiments is available at <https://goo.gl/f9HzP3>. The videos of select experiment trials analysed in this paper are linked in Table S1.

Table S1: Videos referenced in results.

Description	Link
Aggregating swarm. Injected fault is RACT.	https://goo.gl/DKbTWt
Aggregating swarm. Injected fault is ROFS.	https://goo.gl/QrksgZ
Homing swarm. No fault injected.	https://goo.gl/duAFVM

S2 Detection of faulty robots

We conducted five replicates for each combination of task (aggregation, dispersion, and homing) and fault type (PMIN, PMAX, ROFS, LRACT, BACT). The results obtained in the aggregation, dispersion and homing tasks, for each fault type are summarised as radial plots in Figs. S1, S3 and S4, respectively. Each plot indicates the true-positive performance measured as the proportion of time a robot with a fault was detected as behaving abnormally during 30second intervals. The thick solid lines indicate the mean proportion of time that the robot with a fault was correctly labelled as faulty by other robots in the swarm, while the surrounding shaded areas indicate the range (min, max) proportion of time observed in the five replicates.

Figure S1: True-positive results observed in the aggregation task for each fault type averaged over intervals of 30s. Solid line indicates mean percentage of time the robot with an injected fault was classified as behaving abnormally, while shaded area indicates the range (max-min) observed across five replicates of the experiment.

Figure S2: Frames from one of the aggregation experiments in which a fault is injected in the range-and-bearing sensor (ROFS) of robot 0. In the first frame ($t = 1\text{m}45\text{s}$), the faulty robot is correctly detected by the rest of the swarm. In the second frame ($t = 3\text{m}30\text{s}$), the fault is not detected as the robot has become a part of the aggregate, while in the third frame ($t = 4\text{m}30\text{s}$), robot 0 is correctly labelled as faulty (for link to video see Section S1).

Figure S3: True-positive results observed in the dispersion task for fault types, PMIN, PMAX, LRACT, and BACT. We have omitted results of experiments with the ROFS fault, as the range-and-bearing sensor readings were not used for dispersion and therefore a malfunctioning sensor had no influence on the robot's behaviour.

Figure S4: True-positive results observed in the homing task for all fault types. Note that while the shaded areas indicating the range from minimum to maximum performance for the PMIN fault cover the full range in most 30-second intervals, the fault was detected in all replicates. In the replicate where the highest performance was observed, the fault was detected 86.2% of the time, while in the replicate with the lowest performance, the fault was detected 34.8% of the time.

S3 Fault-positive results

Figure S5: The portion of time fully operational robots are incorrectly classified as faulty by the other robots in the swarm performing the aggregation, dispersion and homing tasks. Each dot corresponds to a single robot.

S4 Tolerance to transitions in swarm behaviour

Figure S6: The portion of time fully operational robots switching between tasks are incorrectly classified as faulty by the other robots in the swarm. Each dot corresponds to a single robot. The robots switch from the aggregation to the dispersion task with mean task-switching time of 5 seconds (left) and of 10 seconds (right).